

THE DEVELOPMENT AND DIMENSIONS OF PROFESSIONAL-PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCE IN TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the concept of professional-pedagogical competence, emphasizing its complex nature and the various levels of development throughout a teacher's career. It examines the definitions and classifications of competence, referencing key scholars such as A.K. Markova, N.V. Kuzmina, and S.A. Gaponenko, who highlight different dimensions of competence, including specialized, methodological, social, psychological, and autopsychological. The article discusses how these competences contribute to effective teaching, the teacher's personal growth, and the ability to adapt to professional challenges. Additionally, the article considers the role of postgraduate education in enhancing a teacher's competence and the importance of modeling the structure of competence for future professional development.

РАЗВИТИЕ И АСПЕКТЫ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ В ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ

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ABSTRACT

В данной статье исследуется концепция профессионально-педагогической компетентности, подчеркивается ее комплексный характер и различные уровни развития на протяжении всей карьеры учителя. В ней рассматриваются определения и классификации компетентности со ссылкой на ключевых ученых, таких как А.К. Маркова, Н.В. Кузьмина и С.А. Гапоненко, которые выделяют различные аспекты компетентности, включая специальную, методическую, социальную,

грамотность.

психологическую и аутопсихологическую. В статье обсуждается, как эти компетенции способствуют эффективному преподаванию, личностному росту учителя и способности адаптироваться к профессиональным вызовам. Кроме того, в статье рассматривается роль послевузовского образования в повышении компетентности педагога и важность моделирования структуры компетентности для будущего профессионального развития.

O'QITISHDA KASBIY-PEDAGOGIK KOMPETENTLIK O'LCHAMLARI VA UNI RIVOJLANTIRISH

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ettirishi, funksional savodxonlik.

ABSTRACT

Ushbu maqolada kasbiy-pedagogik kompetentlik tushunchasi o'rganilib, uning murakkab tabiati va o'qituvchi faoliyati davomida rivojlanishning turli darajalari ta'kidlangan. Unda A.K.Markova, N.V.Kuzmina, S.A.Gaponenko kabi yetakchi olimlarning kompetensiyaga bergan ta'riflari va tasniflari ko'rib chiqilgan bo'lib, ular kompetensiyaning turli o'lchamlarini, shu jumladan ixtisoslashgan, uslubiy, ijtimoiy, psixologik va autopsixologik jihatlarni ta'kidlaydilar. Maqolada ushbu kompetensiyalar samarali o'qitish, o'qituvchining shaxsiy o'sishi va kasbiy muammolarga moslashish qobiliyatiga qanday hissa qo'shishi haqida so'z boradi. Shuningdek, maqolada o'qituvchi kompetentligini takomillashtirishda oliy ta'limdan keyingi ta'limning o'rni va kelgusida malaka oshirish uchun kompetentlik tuzilmasini modellashtirishning ahamiyati ko'rib chiqilgan.

According to A.K. Markova (1), the process of competence growth includes entering a specialty, mastering the norms of professional activity and professional communication, having elements of creativity, describing personal experience and passing it on to future generations. However, this process is quite complex, and professional differences may arise due to age-related crises. In this case, at a certain stage, professional aging occurs, due to the closeness to professional development, non-acceptance of the new, exploitation of stereotypes, canonization and universalization of personal experience. When organizing professional development, it is important to substantially determine and compare the level of

competence of the trainee at the entrance and exit, equip him with realistic professional self-esteem and further professional growth opportunities.

V.L. Shapovalov and V.I. Gorovaya interpret the competence of a specialist as a series of manifestations of creativity. And the ways and methods of its formation are seen in the construction of the content of education and the educational process in the higher educational institution (2).

Professional competence, in turn, is the basis for another pedagogical characteristic - functional literacy. Considering the problems of the relationship between general and professional culture as a factor in enhancing pedagogical competence, M.K. Maxlin believes that "a specialist's functional literacy has three levels of formation". The first level (personal) characterizes the suitability for full-fledged performance of any type of labor activity. The second level (personal-professional) indicates suitability for work in the chosen specialty.

The third level (professional-technological) involves the complete mastery of competence and mastery in the chosen activity" (3).

The various aspects of a teacher's professional competence (essence, structure, levels, conditions of formation, etc.) have been the subject of numerous studies by educators and psychologists (K.A. Abulxanova - Slavskaya, O.S. Anisimov, E.P. Belozertsev, G.I. Vergelis, A.V. Gavrilov, N.F. Krivchanskiy, N.V. Kuzmina, L.N. Makarova, N.V. Ostapchuk, G.S. Trofimova and others.

In our point of view, the problem of professional pedagogical competence is considered by modern researchers in accordance with the tradition of analyzing the teacher's qualities, which are important for their successful professional activity, established in domestic pedagogical science. Currently, many researchers include in the concept of professional pedagogical competence the knowledge and skills necessary for carrying out multifaceted educational and upbringing activities.

Today, pedagogy and psychology, as well as other sciences dealing with the problems of higher education, believe that competence is the basis for the successful work of a teacher, including a higher school teacher.

In modern pedagogy, professional-pedagogical competence is understood as an integrative quality of the individual, representing the most adequate, proportional set of professional, communicative, and personal qualities of the teacher, contributing to achieving high-quality results in the learning and upbringing process.

A.K. Markova's concept of pedagogical competence includes all the pedagogical personality traits that ensure a high result in professional activity. To expand the content of this concept, the author includes in it, in addition to pedagogical activity itself, pedagogical communication, as well as the subjective properties of the teacher (4).

I.A. Zimnyaya, along with such factors of pedagogical activity as the physiological (individual) characteristics of the subject, also highlights... "professional-pedagogical and subject knowledge and skills as an indicator of professional competence in the narrow sense of this term". (5).

S.A. Gaponenko understands a teacher's professional-pedagogical competence as "a set of psychological-pedagogical, socio-worldview, and methodological knowledge, as well as

professionally significant qualities that ensure the implementation of pedagogical technologies". (6).

N.V. Kuzmina believes that competence is one of the subjective factors of a teacher's productive activity, along with the type of personality orientation and the level of their abilities.

The author considers professional-pedagogical competence as a teacher's awareness and authority, as a personality trait that allows for the productive solution of educational and upbringing tasks aimed at shaping the personality of another person. The concept of competence is linked to a specific field of activity, in this case, professional-pedagogical (7, p. 87).

Therefore, in modern domestic science, professional pedagogical competence is interpreted as a multi-faceted category.

Based on the analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature devoted to professional competence, as well as in order to solve the tasks of our research, we understand a teacher's psychological and pedagogical competence as a set of personality-significant professional and communicative characteristics and qualities of a teacher that allow for effective pedagogical activity and contribute to achieving high-quality results in the learning process.

Researchers rightly highlight the various types of a teacher's professional competence.

N.V. Kuzmina's classification is based on the fact that the concept of professional-pedagogical competence focuses on the representation of the teacher as a subject of pedagogical influence, capable of structuring scientific and practical knowledge in a special way in order to better solve pedagogical tasks. The main types of professional-pedagogical competence according to N.V. Kuzmina are:

1. Specialized competence in the field of the subject being taught.
2. Methodological competence in the field of methods for forming students' knowledge and skills.
3. Social and psychological competence in the field of communication processes.
4. Differential psychological competence in the field of motives, abilities, orientation of students.
5. Autopsychological competence in the area of merits and disadvantages of one's own activity (8).

A teacher's special competence presupposes their high authority as a scientist, as a representative of a particular science. It includes knowledge, awareness, knowledge of a specific science, its methodology, current state and development prospects. This type of competence also includes the ability to apply scientific knowledge, using it as a tool for influencing students.

The methodological competence of the university teacher is aimed at effectively organizing the pedagogical process and creating new teaching technologies.

Socio-psychological competence is closely linked to the culture of pedagogical communication and the general style of professional behavior of the teacher. It is precisely they that allow him to build his communication with different categories of students in

different ways, achieving necessary changes in the system of their orientation, professional readiness, and competence.

A teacher's differential-psychological competence manifests itself in their ability to build the learning process taking into account the individual characteristics of students. To engage each student in active work not only on studying the subject, but also on themselves as a future professional and creative person, the teacher requires knowledge of the psychology of personality and the psychology of activity, mastery of pedagogical research methods.

A teacher's autopsychological competence lies in knowing themselves as a professional, being able to make adjustments to their activities and communication, taking into account their strengths and weaknesses. The high level of this type of competence is manifested in the teacher's ability to take the position of a researcher in relation to themselves, their activities, and their results.

R.A. Islamshin, examining the system of multi-level training for future teachers, identifies the following types of pedagogical competence: methodological, subject-specific, methodological, and psychological-pedagogical (9).

The methodological aspect of competence was first identified by V.A. Slastenin (10) and represents a system of a teacher's motivational and value-based attitude towards knowledge, understanding its relativity, variability, the ability to engage in the process of constant knowledge exchange, and active participation in the process of continuous education.

A new approach to the formation of subject competence, according to V.A. Adolf, is contained in the existing versions of the standards of higher pedagogical and university education, in which great attention is paid to the system of scientific knowledge necessary for a specialist of higher qualification of different statuses (bachelor, master, higher school teacher) (11).

Methodological competence among various types of pedagogical competence occupies one of the leading positions. It to a certain extent integrates the entire system of special scientific, psychological, pedagogical knowledge and skills and has a clearly expressed applied character. Today, a truly competent teacher can be called one who has an extensive system of knowledge, has his own individual style of activity.

Therefore, the essence of psychological and pedagogical competence lies in the systematic unity of the teacher's psychological and pedagogical knowledge, experience, and qualities that allow for effective pedagogical activity, purposeful organization of pedagogical communication processes, as well as the teacher's personal development and improvement.

The insufficient development of a number of aspects of postgraduate education, the growing relevance, the theoretical and practical significance of its provisions, require defining the forms and methods of forming a teacher's psychological and pedagogical competence based on modeling its structure.

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